

Methodology for identifying and mapping urban forests as nature-based solutions and developing a Sino-European urban forests as nature-based solutions typology (M1.1)

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REFERENCE

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Methodology for identifying and mapping UF-NBS and developing a Sino-European UF-NBS typology (M1.1)

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document describes the envisaged approach for identifying and mapping of cases and projects of urban forests as nature-based solutions (UF-NBS) in European and Chinese cities, and the methodology for developing a typology of UF-NBS.

KEYWORDS

Urban, Nature-based solutions, UF-NBS, methodology, typology, mapping, urban forests

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1 Identification and mapping of UF-NBS in European and Chinese cities

1.1 Objectives

The identification and mapping of cases and projects of urban forests as nature-based solutions (UF-NBS) in European and Chinese cities shall reveal the state-of-the-art in current UF-NBS implementations, identify current trends and novel strategies in UF-NBS and green infrastructure (implementation and planning), and reveal similarities and differences between UF-NBS initiatives in Europe and China.

1.2 UF-NBS identification and mapping approach

Scope and purpose of this identification and mapping approach were discussed with the corresponding group of project partners from EFI, HUB, VUB, UNIBA, CAF-RIF and HKU. As part of this process, various relationships and interdependencies as well as complementarity of outputs between Tasks T1.1 (Identifying and mapping UF-NBS and developing a typology), T1.2 (Reviewing the knowledge on the importance of UF-NBS for resilient cities), T1.4 (Analysing governance, institutional and economic frameworks for UFBS), and T2.1 (Conducting an exploratory analysis of all case studies) were identified and discussed. In this context, most importantly, the scope of Tasks T1.1/T1.2 and T1.4 is not limited to case studies and projects within the case cities of CLEARING HOUSE, but should cover the whole of Europe and China as best as possible. Contrary to that, Task 2.1 focuses specifically on the CLEARING HOUSE case cities. However, there are clear overlaps in the information and data to be collected in each of these Tasks.

As a conclusion, a streamlined data collection is envisaged, which is facilitated by the development of a common, standardized template and a corresponding guidance document. This template (attached) encompasses guiding questions, whereby information on the following key items shall be collected:

- Case study/project key information (title, description etc.), including, e.g., references, photos, potentially point(s) of contact, as well as websites or social media channels if available/applicable;
- Relevant maps to identify the case study/project area and location;
- Objectives and desired impacts;
- Involved stakeholders;
- Relevant policy context, policy documents and/or instruments;
- Compliance with UF-NBS framework as described by the guidance document;
- Transferability, lessons-learned.

This structure of the template should also facilitate the potential integration of collected data into the OPPLA database. This option is to be explored and discussed with OPPLA. In perspective, the template could furthermore be converted into a web-based form if deemed necessary. The standardized template shall subsequently be used by each project partner to collect information on case studies and projects. Here, each partner shall focus primarily on prominent national projects and/or key projects and case studies in their mother tongue.

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The gathered information will then be screened by each of the aforementioned Tasks depending on the objectives of each Task as follows:

- The compilation of the CLEARING HOUSE data repository (i.e., integration of gathered information into the repository) as part of Tasks T1.1/T1.2;
- The analysis of governance, institutional and economic UF-NBS frameworks as part of T1.4;
- The exploratory analysis of all case studies in T2.1.

2 UF-NBS typology development

2.1 Objectives

The UF-NBS typology will be developed by a core group of project partners. It should serve as grounding knowledge for detailed comparative case study analysis, UF-NBS scenario and benchmarking tool development and detailed and standardized inventory of UF-NBS measures relevant in Europe and China, to be fed into the Sino-European co-design event (project month 18). Prior, a draft of the typology is to be discussed with the broader set of project partners, the user advisory group and the stakeholder mirror group, and it is presented and discussed at a workshop at the annual European Forum on Urban Forestry (project month 13).

2.2 Typology development

The UF-NBS is developed in several consecutive steps (Figure 1). In a first step, existing typologies on NBS are screened for their suitability for adaptation. This includes findings from the projects GREEN SURGE (Cvejic et al., 2015), the Nature4Cities project (Nature4Cities, 2018), and of ongoing work within the GreenCityLabHue project at Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin.

The typologies deemed most suitable for adaptation are selected, and subsequently integrated with amended UF-NBS types to evolve them to the peculiar needs of CLEARING HOUSE. This amendment of UF-NBS is done by both the European project partners and the Chinese project partners, to ensure that locally specific UF-NBS measures are included. Findings from the academic and grey literature review carried out in Tasks T1.1 and T1.2 are subsequently included. This ensures that UF-NBS identified by the review of English and Chinese literature are adequately considered.

As a result, a draft UF-NBS typology is created. This draft typology is then discussed with a broader set of project partners, the user advisory group and the stakeholder mirror group, and at the annual European Forum on Urban Forestry. Feedback from these discussions is fed back into the typology to create the finalized UF-NBS typology.

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Figure 1: Workflow of the methodology for the development of the UF-NBS typology.

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CONCLUSION

This document describes the methodologies for developing the UF-NBS typology and for identifying and mapping UF-NBS in European and Chinese cities.

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